

Seasonal population of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers at Varanasi, India

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Leafhoppers and planthoppers are the most dominant insect pests in kharif. The most important of these are *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Sogatella furcifera*, *Recilia dorsalis*, *Tettigella spectra*, and *Nisia atrovenosa*. We recorded seasonal population density changes of these hoppers to determine how to develop management programs for their control.

Thirty rices were grown in a randomized block design with three replications at the BHU research farm in 1981 and 1982. Hopper infestation in 0.5-m² plots was recorded from 15 d after transplanting (DT) to 70 DT.

The figure shows that *Nephotettix* spp., *N. lugens*, and *S. furcifera* populations developed earliest in both years. *T. spectra* also appeared early in 1982 and at 22 DT in 1981. *R. dorsalis* and *N. atrovenosa* occurred first at 50 and 44 DT in 1981 and at 29 and 44 DT in 1982.

There was no relationship between peak population density and crop age. Peak populations developed early in 1981: *S. furcifera* at 37 DT, *N. lugens* at 44 DT, and *Nephotettix* spp. and *T.*

Mean weekly population of different planthoppers per 0.5 m²

Mean weekly population of different leafhoppers per 0.5 m²

spectra at 50 DT. Peak populations of *N. atrovenosa* and *R. dorsalis* were at 58

and 71 DT. In 1982, peak populations occurred later (see figure). □

Mean population density of leafhoppers and planthoppers at Agricultural Research Farm, B. H. U. Varanasi, 1981 and 1982 kharif.

Pest Control and Management WEEDS

Yield improvement and economic return of herbicide application in broadcast rice

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On the Guadalcanal Plains, Solomon Islands, where rice has been grown intensively with heavy mechanization and short turnaround, weeds are a problem and herbicide use is vital to rice production. To estimate the effect of herbicide application (propanil, 360 g ai/litre) on

weed population and rice yield, we conducted a trial in a previously weedy rice field. Major grass species were *Echinochloa colona* and *E. crus-galli*. There were very few broadleaf weeds in the experimental plot. Major broadleaf weeds on the rice farm were *Sphenoclea zeylanica* and *Monochoria vaginalis*.

Five propanil treatments were applied — 2, 3, 4, 5, or 6 litres/ha (0.76, 1.08, 1.44, 1.80, or 2.16 kg ai/ha) — using a knapsack sprayer. Each treatment was replicated 4 times in randomized com-

plete blocks. A 5- × 10-m plot was one replication. To avoid disturbing seedling growth, herbicide was applied from a timber placed across the plot. Ten 1-m swaths were sprayed along the length of the plot.

IR9852-22-3 was seeded on prepared, flooded fields at 120 kg/ha. The field was drained 7 d after seeding (DS). Propanil was applied at 15 DS. Four days after herbicide application, the field was re-flooded. N was applied as urea at 30, 40, and 40 kg N/ha at 30, 50, and 75 DS,

respectively. Weed population was recorded at harvest on four 1-m² quadrats. Yield was recorded from the whole plot.

As propanil dose increased, weed density declined. Rice yield doubled at the lowest herbicide dose and more than tripled at higher doses. In untreated plots, yield loss was 74% (Table 1).

Table 2 shows the effect of weeds on yield components. Yield reduction was highly related to the decrease in panicles/unit area. In heavily infested plots (treatments 1 and 2), rice density was reduced by 1/3 to 1/2 as compared to density with good control (treatment 6), indicating that yield loss was due not only to competition between weeds and rice for soil nutrients and light but also to death of rice seedlings at early growth stages. At about 70 DS, weeds became taller than rice plants, reducing photosynthesis at preflowering and grain formation. Spikelets/panicle and percentage empty spikelets were significantly reduced in untreated and low-dose plots. Weight of 1,000 grains was not affected by weed

Table 1. Herbicide application and economic return for irrigated, broadcast rice, Solomon Islands.^a

Treatment	Dosage (kg ai/ha) of propanil	Weeds/m ² (no.)	Yield (t/ha)	Yield loss (%)	Gain ^b (US\$/ha)
1	0	505 d	1.1 d	74	—
2	0.76	207 c	2.1 c	52	210
3	1.08	64 b	3.6 b	18	550
4	1.44	22 ab	4.2 ab	6	670
5	1.80	10 ab	3.9 ab	11	615
6	2.16	1 a	4.4 a	—	723

^aSeparation of means by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level. ^bGain was estimated by comparing with yield of the untreated plots, using current prices on paddy (\$225/t) and propanil (Stam F34 e.c.) (\$2.90/litre).

Table 2. Yield and yield components of broadcast rice at different weed densities,^a Solomon Islands.

Treatment	Panicles/m ²	Grains/panicle (no.)	% empty grain	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
1	160 c	50 b	22 a	29 a	1.1 d
2	207 bc	55 b	27 b	30 a	2.1 c
3	293 ab	60 ab	25 ab	30 a	3.6 b
4	331 ab	77 a	23 a	30 a	4.2 ab
5	273 b	74 a	24 ab	28 a	3.9 b
6	376 a	71 a	24 ab	29 a	4.4 a

^a Means of four 50-m² plots served as 4 replications. Yield components were obtained from 5 plants in each replication, Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

infestation. Broadleaf weeds did not affect crop growth because seedling

establishment was good and homogeneous. □

Efficiency of herbicide carriers for lowland rice weed control

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We studied the efficiency of herbicide carriers for weed control in the All India Coordinated Research Programme on Weed Control in 1984 wet season at TNAU. An emulsifiable concentrate (EC) formulation of thiobencarb at 1.5 kg/ha was mixed with easily available carriers: farmyard manure (2, 4, or 6 kg/ha), rice bran and husk (2, 4, or 6 kg/ha), soil (12.5, 25, or 50 kg/ha), sand (50 kg/ha), or water (750 litres/ha) and applied 5 d after transplanting (DT) with 3 to 5 cm standing water in the field. The mixtures were compared with a control pre-emergence sprinkle application of oxadiazon EC (0.48 or 0.72 kg/ha) and an unweeded control,

In the control plots, weed density/m² at 30 and 50 DT was 50 and 196 for *Echinochloa crus-galli* (L.) Beauv., 22

Efficiency of herbicide carriers for weed control on rice, Coimbatore, India.

Carrier and quantity per ha		Treatment	Weed wt ^a (g/m ²)		Productive tillers (no./5 plants)	Grain yield (t/ha)
		Preemergence herbicide and dose (kg/ha)	30 DT	50 DT		
Farmyard manure		Thiobencarb				
	2 kg	1.5	48	124	57	5.2
	4 kg	1.5	46	112	63	5.6
Rice bran and husk	6 kg	1.5	22	153	61	5.5
	2 kg	1.5	31	93	53	5.3
	4 kg	1.5	15	123	58	5.8
Soil	6 kg	1.5	41	119	59	5.7
	12.5 kg	1.5	43	147	57	5.3
	25 kg	1.5	66	108	57	5.8
Sand, 50 kg	50 kg	1.5	24	84	60	5.0
	Water, 500 litres	1.5	34	132	54	5.8
	EC formulation	1.5	26	166	59	5.4
direct spraying		Oxadiazon				
	4 litres	0.48	36	178	58	4.7
	6 litres	0.72	28	120	64	5.9
No herbicide or weeding	—		84	300	49	3.2
CD			6	8	1	0.5

^a DT = days after transplanting.

and 32 for *Paspalum* sp., 18 and 126 for *Cyperus difformis* (L.), 6 and 18 for *Marsilea quadrifolia* L., and 28 and 8 for *Monochoria vaginalis* L. Thiobencarb

with different carriers at all rates effectively controlled annual grasses and sedges, but not *Paspalum* sp.

Treatments reduced weed dry matter